

Electrical Conducting Behavior of Hybrid Nanocomposites Containing Carbon Nanotubes and Carbon Black

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Abstract

Nanocomposites reinforced with hybrid fillers of carbon nanotube (CNT) and carbon black (CB) were developed, aiming at enhancing the electrical conductivity of the composites with balanced mechanical properties while lowering the cost of the final product. Epoxy-based nanocomposites were successfully prepared with varying combinations of CNT and CB as conductive fillers and their electrical and mechanical properties were evaluated. It was shown that adding CB in CNT composites can enhance the electrical conductivity of the composites: a low percolation threshold was achieved with 0.20 wt% CNTs and 0.20 wt% of CB. CB enhanced the ductility of the nanocomposites, confirming the synergic effect of CB as an effective multi-functional filler. Flexural modulus and strength were remained at around 3.30 GPa and 110 MPa, respectively, between the composites containing CNT only and those filled with hybrid fillers. The implications of the findings are discussed regarding practical applications of the composites as the thermal interface material for electronics packaging.

1. Introduction

Electrical conducting polymers are considered to be an important group of relatively inexpensive materials for many engineering applications [1-2], such as electrical conductive adhesives, antistatic coatings and films, electromagnetic interference shielding materials for electronic devices, thermal interface materials, etc. Conventional conducting fillers are usually micrometer-scale metal powder, carbon black, or carbon fibres. In order to achieve the percolation threshold and satisfactory electrical conductivity, the conventional filler content needs to be as high as 15 to 50wt%, which results in a composite with poor mechanical properties and high density. Use of nano-scale conducting fillers, such as carbon nanofiber, carbon nanotubes and graphite nanoplatelet, to replace the conventional fillers has proven to be effective to significantly reduce the filler content required for adequate conductivity and to minimize the problems associated with mechanical properties [2-5]. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in particular have attracted much attention as the electrical conducting filler for conducting composites. The percolation threshold of CNT reinforced polymer nanocomposites is found much lower than those containing conventional micro-scale conducting fillers because of its inherently high conductivity, high aspect ratio and high specific surface area [3]. The potential of employing CNTs as conducting filler has, however, been severely limited

because of the difficulties for dispersion of entangled CNTs during processing, especially when the CNT content is higher than about 1.0wt%, and the high cost of CNTs.

In this study, nanocomposites containing hybrid fillers of CNTs and carbon black (CB) were developed, aiming at enhancing the electrical conductivity of the composites and while significantly lowering the cost of the final product. The electrical and mechanical properties of the composites were evaluated, and the implications of the findings were discussed regarding practical applications of the nanocomposites in electronics packaging industry.

2. Experiment

2.1 Materials and composite fabrication

CNTs used in this study were prepared by a chemical vapor deposition method (multi-walled CNTs, supplied by Iljin Nanotech Ltd., Korea). The diameter and length ranged between 10–20 nm and 10–50 μ m, respectively, according to the supplier's specification. Carbon black (VULCAN XC72R, Cabot Corp.) was used as another conducting filler. The diameter was in the range of 20-60 nm according to the TEM observation.

The composites were made from epoxy, a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA, Epon 828, Shell Chemical), and a curing agent, m-phenylenediamine (mPDA, Sigma-Aldrich). Figure 1 shows the processing steps used to fabricate the nanocomposites containing different fractions of CNT and CB reinforcements. The fillers and DGEBA were mixed into 200 ml acetone, and then the mixture was dispersed using a high-speed shear mixer (HSM-100L, Ross) at 3000 rpm for 1h. The mixture was distilled at 80 °C to remove the solvent, which was followed by degassing in a vacuum oven at 80 °C for 5 h to eliminate the entrapped air. The mPDA hardener was added into the mixture in the ratio of 14.5/100 by weight while gently stirring the mixture. The composite was molded into a flat plate and cured at 80 °C for 2 h, followed by post cure at 150 °C for 2 h.

2.2 Characterization method

The bulk electrical conductivity of nanocomposites was measured at room temperature using a programmable curve tracer (Sony Tektronix 370A). 10mm x 10mm square specimens were cut from the plate, which were polished on both sides into a thickness of 0.8 mm. Silver paste was applied to minimize the contact resistance between the composite sample and the electrodes. Three-point flexure test was

performed to measure the mechanical properties of neat epoxy and nanocomposites according to the specification, ASTM Standard D790. The molded nanocomposite plates were cut into 50 mm long \times 12.7 mm wide \times 1 mm thick specimens, which were subjected to bending with a support span of 25.4 mm at a constant cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min on a universal testing machine (MTS Sintech 10/D). Five specimens were tested for each set of conditions. A scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL-6700 F) was employed to exam the fracture morphologies of nanocomposites.

Figure 1. Fabrication process for the epoxy-based nanocomposites.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites

The electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites is plotted as a function of filler content in Figure 2. The incorporation of CNT alone increased the conductivity of composite almost nine orders of magnitude, from 5.6×10^{-13} S/cm to 8.3×10^{-4} S/cm, when the CNT content was increased from 0 to 1.0 wt% with a percolation threshold at about 0.30 wt% (Fig. 2A). This observation is consistent with our previous work on CNT nanocomposites based on a similar matrix material [3, 4]. However, for the same range of filler content, the nanocomposite with CB exhibited a much smaller - about six orders of magnitude - improvement in conductivity. A further increase of CB content from 1.0 to 4.0 wt% contributed only a marginal increase in conductivity. The poor performance on electrical conductivity of CB composites compared to the CNT counterpart was expected. The major reason responsible for this observation is due to the spherical shape of CB with its very low aspect ratio, which makes them difficult to form conducting networks in the polymer [3].

Further experiments were carried out to investigate the influence of hybrid fillers on conductivity. Hybrid nanocomposites were prepared by adding varying CB contents into the composites with two different fixed CNT contents of 0.20 and 0.40 wt%, corresponding to those below and above the percolation threshold, respectively. Fig. 2B presents the conductivity plotted as a function of CB content for composites with 0.20 wt% CNT. The electrical conductivity increased from 9.42×10^{-13} S/cm to 2.75×10^{-7} S/cm before the percolation threshold with only additional 0.20 wt% of CB. A further increase of CB content from 0.40 wt% to 2.0 wt% did not much enhance the conductivity, suggesting a saturated conductivity in the range of CB contents studied. When varying amounts of CB were added into the nanocomposites

with a fixed 0.40 wt% CNT (Fig. 2C), there was only a marginal positive effect of electrical conductivity improvement.

Figure 2. Electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites containing fillers of different contents. (A: composites filled with CNT or CB only; B: composites filled with 0.20 wt% CNT and varying CB content; C: composites filled with 0.40 wt% CNT and varying CB content)

Figure 3 presents schematics of conducting networks in the nanocomposites containing hybrid fillers with different geometries. In the nanocomposites containing CB only (Fig. 3A), the fillers are dispersed randomly, but conducting pathways cannot be formed if the filler contents are below the percolation threshold (about 0.80 wt%, see Fig. 2A). Even at the CB contents above the percolation threshold, the conductivity will not be high because of the point-point contact of these spherical particles; and the conductivity

increases gradually as the CB content increases above the threshold value. The nanocomposite containing CNT only has a very low percolation threshold (Fig. 3B). When CB nanoparticles are added into the nanocomposites containing CNTs (Fig. 3C), the gaps between the CNTs are effectively filled and the CNTs are linked together, resulting in the formation of tight conducting networks. This ameliorating effect of CB particles on the network formation is more pronounced when the CNT content is below the percolation threshold (Fig. 2B).

Figure 3. Schematics of conducting networks in nanocomposites containing hybrid fillers with different geometries (A: composites filled with CB only; B: composites filled with CNT only; C: composites filled with hybrid CB and CNT).

3.2 Mechanical properties of the nanocomposites

Table 1 summarizes the mechanical properties of the nanocomposites. Both the flexural modulus and strength did not show drastic changes within the data scattering when either CNTs or CB particles were added. The relatively low modulus and strength obtained here for the nanocomposites containing CNT alone compared to our previous studies [4] are attributed to the fact that CNTs were not properly functionalized in this study in an effort to maintain a high electrical conductivity. Functionalization with silane coupling agents resulted in a significant reduction in CNT conductivity due to wrapping of CNTs with polymer layers [4].

Table 1. Flexural modulus, strength and ductility of neat epoxy and nanocomposites

Filler and wt%	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Extension (mm)
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Neat epoxy	3.34±0.08	109.6±3.4	4.31±1.4 2
0.20% CNT	3.41±0.11	117.8±8.1	6.20±1.5 5
0.40% CNT	3.13±0.13	119.0±3.3	9.66±0.6 7
1.0% CNT	3.16±0.23	121.8±3.9	7.68±1.2 9
0.20% CB	3.30±0.06	104.6±2.6	10.50 *
0.40% CB	3.26±0.13	109.5±4.5	10.50 *
1.0% CB	3.36±0.07	115.0±3.5	10.50 *
2.0% CB	3.51±0.14	107.5±4.9	10.50 *
0.20% CNT + 0.20% CB	3.37±0.17	114.8±2.5	10.50 *
0.20% CNT + 0.40% CB	3.49±0.17	106.7±3.9	10.50 *
0.20% CNT + 1.0% CB	3.21±0.08	115.6±2.0	10.50 *
0.20% CNT + 2.0% CB	3.11±0.17	94.6±3.0	10.50 *
0.40% CNT + 0.40% CB	3.21±0.14	110.4±5.3	10.50 *
0.40% CNT + 1.0% CB	3.29±0.09	108.1±3.3	10.50 *
0.40% CNT + 2.0% CB	3.43±0.13	106.4±3.9	10.50 *

* No failure under the maximum extension.

Incorporation of CB particles into the neat epoxy or CNT nanocomposite had added benefits of enhancing the ductility of nanocomposites. Figure 4 shows typical load-displacement curves of the nanocomposites. The CNT nanocomposite (Fig. 4B) showed higher ductility than the neat epoxy (Fig. 4A) before catastrophic failure. It is interesting to note that when CB was introduced into the CNT-epoxy system, the hybrid nanocomposites withstood much larger deformation than the other systems before fracture (Fig. 4C). These observations suggest that i) CB played an important role in changing the fracture behavior the nanocomposites from brittle to ductile failure; and ii) hybridization with CB particles improved the fracture resistance, enhancing the energy dissipation capacity of the nanocomposites.

Figure 4. Load-displacement curve of the nanocomposites filled with different fillers.

3.3 Fractured surface morphology of nanocomposites

Figure 5. Fracture morphology of the nanocomposites (A: Neat Epoxy; B and D: Composites containing 0.40% CNT; C and E: Composites containing 0.4 % CNT+ 1.0% CB).

Figure 5 presents a series of SEM images taken from the fractured surfaces of the nanocomposites. The neat epoxy (Fig. 5A) exhibited a smooth, mirror-like fracture surface representing brittle failure of a homogeneous material. In sharp contrast, when CNT (Fig. 5B) and CB (Fig. 5C) were added into the system, the fracture surface became irregular and rough: river-like markings appeared, and this became more pronounced with the addition of CB particles (Fig. 5C and 5E). It is thought that the number of these markings roughly corresponded to the number of dispersed CNTs and CB, which forced the cracks to propagate bypassing these fillers and taking a long path, in the so-called pinning and

crack-tip bifurcation effects, resulting in higher energy dissipation. These observations are quite consistent with the corresponding load-displacement curves in Fig. 4.

4. Conclusions and Perspectives

In summary, epoxy-based nanocomposites containing hybrid fillers of CNT and CB were developed. The electrical and mechanical properties of the composites were evaluated. It was shown that adding hybrid fillers of CB and CNTs can enhance the electrical conductivity of the nanocomposites. CB also improved significantly the ductility of the hybrid nanocomposites while maintaining high modulus and strength, confirming the synergic effect of CB as an effective multi-functional filler. The findings of this work also suggest potential applications of the hybrid nanocomposites in the electronics packaging industry as the electrical conducting adhesives and pastes. Thermal interface material is another important area where the hybrid nanocomposites can find widespread applications. The thermal conducting behavior of the hybrid nanocomposites is the subject of our future work in a large project based on the functional properties of CNT-polymer nanocomposites.

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